

Measuring the Impact of Facebook and Instagram Reels Among Young Adults

*A Study of Usage Patterns, Creativity,
Productivity and Mental Well-being
of Youth in Bihar*

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ABSTRACT

Social media has transformed the way young adults communicate, consume information, and spend their leisure time. Among the most popular digital features, Facebook and Instagram Reels have emerged as influential short-form video platforms that significantly shape the behaviour, creativity, and lifestyle of young users. While these platforms provide opportunities for entertainment, self-expression, learning, and content creation, their excessive use has also raised concerns regarding productivity, attention span, mental well-being, and social interaction.

This study examines the impact of Facebook and Instagram Reels on young adults in Bihar, India, with a particular focus on usage patterns, creativity, productivity, and mental well-being. A quantitative research design was adopted, and primary data were collected through a structured online questionnaire administered to 60 respondents aged between 15 and 30 years. The collected data were analysed to identify behavioural trends and the perceived positive and negative effects associated with short-form video consumption.

The findings reveal that Facebook and Instagram Reels serve as valuable platforms for entertainment, knowledge sharing, skill development, and creative expression. However, prolonged and uncontrolled usage was found to contribute to reduced productivity, increased screen dependency, diminished real-life social interaction, and psychological concerns such as stress, anxiety, and social comparison. The study highlights the dual nature of short-form video platforms, demonstrating that their impact depends largely on users' patterns of engagement and digital habits.

The research concludes that responsible and balanced use of social media is essential for maximising its educational and creative benefits while minimising its potential risks. The findings may contribute to future research in digital media studies and provide useful insights for educators, parents, policymakers, and young social media users seeking healthier digital engagement.

KEYWORDS

Facebook Reels; Instagram Reels; Social Media; Short-form Video; Young Adults; Digital Media; Creativity; Productivity; Mental Well-being; Bihar

INTRODUCTION

In the digital era, social media has transformed the way people communicate, access information, express themselves, and spend their free time. Its influence is particularly strong among the youth, who are the most active users of digital platforms. Among the many social networking platforms available today, Facebook and Instagram stand out as two of the most widely used, with millions of active users globally. Facebook, launched in 2004 by Mark Zuckerberg and his Harvard classmates, began as a campus-based networking tool and quickly expanded to become one of the world's largest digital platforms. Instagram, launched in 2010 and later acquired by Facebook (now Meta Platforms, Inc.) in 2012, gained rapid popularity due to its emphasis on visual storytelling through photos and videos.

With the rapid rise in the popularity of short-form video content, driven largely by platforms like TikTok, Instagram introduced Reels in August 2020 as a direct response. Facebook followed suit by launching Facebook Reels in 2022, bringing short-form videos to a broader user base. These features allow users to create and watch short, engaging videos ranging from 15 to 60 seconds. Reels cover a wide variety of content such as fashion, dance, music, fitness, cooking, comedy, motivational talks, educational tutorials, and trending challenges. Their visual appeal, brevity, and ease of sharing make them incredibly attractive to young audiences who are constantly seeking quick entertainment and new trends.

For youth aged 15 to 30, Reels have become more than just a form of entertainment—they are part of a larger social experience. Young people use Reels for a variety of purposes, including following viral trends, expressing creativity, learning new skills, and building online communities. Some even see Reels as a potential career path, becoming content creators or influencers who gain followers, sponsorships, and even income. Reels provide an opportunity for visibility, validation, and influence—all of which are highly valued by the digitally connected younger generation.

However, this rising engagement with Reels also brings with it a number of challenges and concerns. The highly addictive nature of short-form videos, combined with algorithmic

recommendations that constantly suggest new content, can lead to excessive screen time. Many youths report spending hours on Reels, often at the expense of sleep, studies, or real-world social interactions. Additionally, the curated and idealised nature of many Reels promotes unrealistic beauty standards and lifestyles, leading to social comparison, dissatisfaction, and mental health issues such as anxiety, depression, and low self-esteem.

Furthermore, the pressure to stay relevant online or to produce "viral" content can increase stress and feelings of inadequacy among youth. Some experience a fear of missing out (FOMO), while others may struggle with online criticism or cyberbullying. The quick and repetitive format of Reels may also contribute to shorter attention spans and reduced focus in academic or work-related tasks.

Nevertheless, it is important to acknowledge the positive aspects of Reels. When used mindfully, Reels can be a source of creativity, motivation, and learning. They allow youth to share knowledge, spread awareness about social issues, engage with like-minded communities, and explore career opportunities in digital media. For many young users, especially those in rural or less privileged areas, Reels offer a platform to voice their opinions, showcase their talents, and gain recognition beyond geographical limitations.

The impact of Facebook and Instagram Reels is, therefore, multi-dimensional. While they offer significant benefits in terms of creativity, communication, and opportunity, they also pose risks related to overuse, distraction, and mental well-being. This dissertation aims to explore the dual nature of Reels by focusing on their real-life effects on youth.

The primary aim of this study is to investigate how frequently youth engage with Facebook and Instagram Reels, the purposes behind their usage, and the psychological, social, and cultural outcomes of this engagement. The study adopts a quantitative research approach using an online questionnaire to collect primary data from young adults in Bihar.

This research does not seek to label Reels as inherently positive or negative, but rather to understand how youth interact with this form of content, what motivates their engagement, and what outcomes emerge from prolonged usage. The findings will offer insights for youth, parents, educators, and policymakers on how to encourage healthy digital habits and reduce the risks associated with unregulated social media consumption in the age of short-form video content.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Social media platforms like Facebook and Instagram have become a big part of everyday life, especially for young people. One of the most popular features on these platforms is “Reels,” which are short videos that users can easily create and share. These videos are fun, trendy, and often go viral. Because of this, youth spend a lot of time watching or making Reels. While Reels offer entertainment and creative opportunities, there are also growing concerns about their effects on the mental, emotional, and social well-being of young people.

Many youth between the ages of 15 to 30 watch Reels daily—sometimes for many hours. Some do it for fun, others to relax, and some even use it as a way to escape from stress or boredom. However, this frequent use can lead to problems like screen addiction, poor time management, and lack of focus. Students may spend more time watching Reels than studying, and working individuals may feel distracted during work hours. These habits can reduce productivity and affect their goals in life.

Another issue is the pressure to follow trends and show a perfect lifestyle on social media. Many Reels show luxury, beauty, or talent in a way that can make others feel insecure or not good enough. Young people may start comparing themselves to others, which can lead to stress, anxiety, or low self-esteem. Also, when youth see influencers getting fame and money through Reels, they might feel that success is only about looks, likes, or followers—this can change their thinking and values.

On the other hand, Reels also have a positive side. They allow youth to explore their creativity, learn new things, and express themselves. Many people use Reels to show talents like dancing, acting, cooking, or singing. Some even build careers through content creation. So, Reels are not just for entertainment—they can also be tools for learning and growth.

The main problem here is not whether Reels are good or bad, but how they are being used. There is a lack of proper understanding about the impact of Reels on youth’s lifestyle, creativity, productivity, and mental health. Most young users do not think about how much time they are spending or what kind of content they are watching. Also, parents, teachers, and society are still trying to understand the real effect of this new digital trend.

Therefore, this research aims to explore the deeper impact of Facebook and Instagram Reels on youth. It will study both the benefits and the possible risks. By doing so, the research hopes to bring more awareness and help youth find a balanced and healthy way to use Reels. This study is important because youth are the future of our society, and understanding their behavior on social media will help in guiding them towards better choices.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE RESEARCH

Social media has become an important part of life, especially for young people. Among all the features available on social media, Facebook and Instagram Reels have gained massive popularity. These short videos are quick, fun, and engaging, which makes youth spend a lot of time on them. While Reels provide entertainment and new ways to express creativity, they also come with certain risks. This study is important because it helps us understand both the positive and negative effects of Reels on youth aged 15 to 30.

This research is significant for many reasons:

1. Understanding Youth Behavior

Today's youth are growing up in a digital world. This study will help us understand how young people are spending their time online, especially with short video content. By knowing how often and why they use Reels, we can understand their habits and online behavior better. This information can help educators, parents, and policymakers guide youth in a positive direction.

2. Exploring the Impact on Lifestyle and Productivity

Many people believe that social media is reducing productivity and creating distractions. But this idea needs to be properly studied and proven. This research will show how Reels affect the daily life of youth—whether they help them relax and learn or lead to poor time management and loss of focus. The findings can help students and working youth reflect on their own media usage.

3. Highlighting Mental Health and Social Concerns

Reels can also affect how youth feel about themselves and others. Constant comparison with influencers or watching unrealistic content can lead to anxiety, stress, or feelings of low self-worth. This study will shine a light on such issues and help spread awareness about the importance of mental health in the digital age.

4. Supporting Positive Use of Reels

This study is not only about the problems but also about the benefits of Reels. Many young people use Reels to learn new skills, share their talents, and even start small businesses. The study will highlight these positive examples, showing how social media can be a tool for growth, confidence, and creativity when used properly.

5. Helping Future Research and Policy

This research can be useful for future scholars, educators, and digital media experts. It provides real data from youth users and helps in building a foundation for more detailed studies in the future. The results can also help social media platforms understand their young audience better and make changes that encourage safe and healthy use.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A literature review helps us understand what earlier researchers have already discovered about a topic. It builds a background and gives us direction for further research. In this review, we look at important studies about social media usage, especially focusing on Facebook and Instagram Reels and their impact on youth.

Anderson and Jiang (2018) found that over 90% of teenagers and young adults use social media daily. Their study revealed that platforms like Instagram and Facebook are not just used for fun but are deeply connected to how youth communicate, express themselves, and stay informed.

Kuss and Griffiths (2017) explored how overuse of social media can become addictive. Their study showed that algorithms are made to keep users hooked by showing personalised content. This is especially true for Reels, where one video leads to another, making it hard to stop.

Smith (2020) focused on short video formats like Reels. He discussed how these videos shape youth behaviour by spreading fashion trends, lifestyle ideas, and popular challenges. This affects how young people think, dress, and behave.

Kapoor and Bansal (2021) showed a more positive angle. Their study explained how Reels can be a platform for youth entrepreneurship. Many young people use Reels to promote their business ideas, showcase their talents, and improve their confidence.

World Health Organization (2022) released data warning about the dangers of too much screen time. Youth who spend long hours on Reels may develop anxiety, loneliness, and sleep problems. This affects their emotional and physical well-being.

O'Reilly et al. (2018) studied how social media creates emotional stress. The need for likes, shares, and views affects self-esteem. Young people often feel pressured to post content that gets attention, which can lead to anxiety and sadness.

Montag et al. (2021) explored the effect of Reels on brain behaviour. They found that short, fast videos can affect attention spans. Youth may find it harder to concentrate on studies or long reading tasks after frequent exposure to such content.

Arora and Kumar (2020) focused on influencer culture. They found that Reels often promote content from popular creators. Youth start copying these influencers' styles, slang, and opinions, which can reduce individuality.

Sharma and Gupta (2022) highlighted how local creators use Reels to spread regional culture and language. This is one of the few studies showing how Reels can preserve and promote traditional culture and connect communities.

Chand & Sethi (2019) emphasised that Reels provide a new form of digital storytelling. Young people are using this medium to talk about their personal lives, social issues, and even raise awareness about important topics.

Verma (2021) studied how Reels are used for brand marketing. Young audiences are being targeted with visual ads through influencers. This affects how they make purchasing decisions and shapes their consumer habits.

Banerjee & Mishra (2020) analysed the relationship between social media engagement and self-worth. Youth tend to compare themselves with others online, and this comparison can lead to feelings of jealousy, failure, and low confidence.

Singh & Thakur (2022) conducted a study on student performance. They found that spending too much time on Reels has reduced time for studies, resulting in poor academic performance and lack of focus.

Bansal (2018) argued that social media is shifting attention from reading to visual content. Youth are spending more time watching than reading, which might hurt their ability to learn deeply and concentrate over long periods.

Joshi & Mehta (2023) looked at youth who gained sudden popularity through Reels. These youth often felt pressure to maintain their fame by constantly posting new content. This creates stress, emotional burnout, and a feeling of not being able to take a break.

Although previous studies have examined social media usage, addiction, influencer culture, and digital behaviour, limited research has specifically explored the combined impact of Facebook and Instagram Reels on creativity, productivity, and mental well-being among young adults in Bihar. Therefore, the present study attempts to address this gap.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The theoretical framework is the base of any research. It includes the theories and concepts that help us understand and explain the topic better. For this study on “**Facebook and Instagram Reels and Their Impact on Youth,**” we will use a few communication and media-related theories. These theories help us understand how Reels influence youth behavior, thinking, and lifestyle.

1. Uses and Gratifications Theory

This is one of the most important theories used in media studies. It says that people use media for their own personal needs. In simple words, we don’t just watch videos or use social media by chance—we use it because it gives us something we want.

In the case of Reels, youth use them for different reasons:

- To get entertained
- To pass time
- To learn something new
- To express their creativity
- To stay connected with trends and peers

This theory helps us understand why youth are attracted to Reels and what benefits they feel they get from watching or creating them.

2. Social Comparison Theory

This theory was introduced by psychologist Leon Festinger. It says that people often compare themselves with others, especially in terms of lifestyle, beauty, success, or popularity. Social media, especially Reels, shows a lot of “perfect” lives—good looks, luxury, fame, and talent. When young users watch these, they may start comparing themselves and feel low or pressured.

This theory helps us understand why some youth feel anxiety or low self-esteem after spending time on Reels. It shows how social media can affect our emotions and self-image.

3. Cultivation Theory

This theory, given by George Gerbner, says that people who watch a lot of media may start believing the media world is the real world. For example, if a youth watches hundreds of Reels showing rich lifestyles or perfect relationships, they may start believing that this is normal and expected in real life.

This theory helps us understand how long-term exposure to Reels can change the way youth think, behave, or expect things from life. It also helps in understanding how trends and viral content shape youth culture and beliefs.

4. Media Dependency Theory

This theory says that people depend on media to understand their social environment and make decisions. During stressful times, like the COVID-19 pandemic, many youth turned to Reels for comfort, fun, and information. The more they depend on Reels, the more powerful the platform becomes in influencing their choices and opinions.

This theory helps explain the growing emotional and social connection youth have with platforms like Facebook and Instagram through Reels.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES:

The main purpose of this study is to understand how Facebook and Instagram Reels are affecting the lives of young people. As Reels have become a big trend among youth, it is important to know how and why they are being used, and what changes they bring in the daily routine, thinking, and behavior of young users.

This research has been planned with the following clear and focused objectives:

- 1. To understand the frequency and purpose of Facebook and Instagram Reels usage among youth.**
- 2. To analyze their impact on lifestyle, creativity, and productivity.**
- 3. To identify potential negative outcomes such as addiction, social isolation, or mental health challenges.**
- 4. To explore the role of Reels in shaping youth culture and online interactions.**

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a quantitative research approach.

The survey method is used for data collection. The tool of data collection is a questionnaire.

The survey is conducted digitally through Google Forms. This data provided the research with individual-level opinions of students sharing their perspective about the credibility of digital media platforms. whereas the secondary data available on reliable digital platforms is used for a better understanding.

There are two types of survey: descriptive survey and analytical survey. An analytical survey was used to conduct this research.

The analytical survey seeks to determine why people behave in particular ways. Researchers use analytical surveys to test what causes certain kind of behaviour.

Analytical surveys attempt to determine whether there is causal relationship between certain kinds of behaviour and various social and demographic characteristics of people.

The youth of Bihar aged between 15 to 30 were chosen as the population of this study, as the Bihar consists of diverse and vibrant Youth and is the perfect space for conducting a survey on credibility of Facebook and Instagram Reels and Youth and knowing the Impact of It on Youth.

A random sampling method was used to maintain the diversity of opinions and perspectives throughout the survey. As the main concern of this research is to understand the Impact of Reels and short-forms videos on youth. As they are the ones exposed to Facebook and Instagram Reels every second.

For this survey, The sample consisted of 60 respondents.

This survey provided clear insights into the perspectives of Bihari youth regarding the impact of Reels. Survey through the questionnaire was held which included the close-ended questions, that helps in exploring mind directly.

The data for this research has been collected from both primary and secondary sources. To record the personal opinion and perspective of an individual and also to attain an in-depth knowledge and understanding. Personal opinion helps in examining the perspective of youth

for recognizing the Impact of Facebook and Instagram reels available online. Whereas the in-depth knowledge makes the study more credible and provides more data

The primary data was collected through a survey consisting of close-ended questions to examine the youth's opinion clearly. Whereas the secondary data included the research paper and articles available online.

A survey was conducted using questionnaire as the tool. The questionnaire was distributed among the young adults aged majorly from 15-30 of Bihar. The results of questionnaire have been used to evaluate and bring the findings to a conclusion.

For data collection, certain things have been kept in mind to analyse the research and take the research forward:

- ❖ To analyse the usage behaviour of users of Facebook and Instagram.
- ❖ To identify the Impact of short-form videos on Facebook and Instagram.
- ❖ Factors influencing the user's addiction from Reels of Facebook and Instagram.
- ❖ Lack of focus due to short of videos.

FINDINGS

SURVEY TO COLLECT RESPONDENTS' OPINION:

The research was conducted and analysed according to the described objectives of the research on observing the Impact on youth through short videos and a survey analyse the young minds.

The following are the findings of the research:

As per the first objective, **To understand the frequency and purpose of Facebook and Instagram Reels usage among youth, the findings are;**

The uses of Facebook and Instagram Reels among youth

Figure-1, illustrates the frequency of Facebook and Instagram Reels usage among young adults. Here, 63.3% of youth watching multiple time reels in a day, 15% watching once or twice in a day, 10% watching occasionally and 8.3% watching reels a few times in a weak.

Spending Daily Time to watching Reels or Short Videos.

Figure- 2, Daily Time Spent Watching Reels. Here, 31.7% of youth spending 1-2 hrs., 20% more then 2 hrs., 20% 30-60 minutes, 16.7% 10-30 minutes, and 11.7% spending less than 10 minutes in a day.

Primary Reason for watching Reels.

Figure-3, Primary Reasons for Watching Reels, 44 respondents said they watch reels for entertainment, 28 respondent said they are watching reels for time pass, 24 said they watching to learning new things, 13 said they following trends, and 6 said that they have other reason for watching reels like: interest, yt shorts, relaxation, social media updates.

Objective: 02, To analyze their impact on lifestyle, creativity, and productivity.

Watching Reels helped to learning new things.

Figure-4, represents the Reels helped youngsters to learn new Creative things. 36.7% of respondent agreed with my question, 25% neutral, 20% Disagreed, 11.7% of respondent Strongly Disagreed, and remaining respondent strongly agreed with my sentence.

Watching Reels wastes a lot of time.

Figure-5, represents watching reels wastes a lot of time, 38% of people agreed about my sentence that Reels wastes a lot of time. 30% of people Strongly agreed, 23% of people neutral, remaining people said Disagreed and strongly Disagreed.

Reels have influenced daily habits and lifestyle.

Figure-6, represents the daily habits and lifestyle. 43.3% of people agreed with my response, 25% of respondent neutral, 15% Disagreed, 13.3% strongly agreed with my sentence, and other strongly agreed with this sentence.

Objective 03: To identify potential negative outcomes such as addiction, social isolation, or mental health challenges

Reels or short videos cause addiction.

Figure-7, represents the Reels and Short Video cause addiction. 35% agreed, 23.3% neutral, 16.7% Agreed, 16.7% Disagreed, and 8.3% Strongly Disagreed.

Watching Reels reduces real-life social interactions.

Figure-8, Watching reels has reduces real-life social interaction. 38.3% of respondents agreed with my statement, 23.3% of respondents neutral with it, 20% Disagreed, and 11.7% Strongly agreed with the statement Reels has reduced real-life social interaction.

Watching Reels has affected the mental health of youth.

Figure-9, Watching Reels has affected the mental health of youth, 31.7% of youth agreed with this statement, 30% neutral, 20% disagreed, 11.7% of youth Said Strongly Negative (Increasing stress/anxiety), remaining said Strongly Positive (Make them happy & Motivated)

Objective 4: To explore the role of Reels in shaping youth culture and online interactions

Reels have influenced youth's fashion, speech or lifestyles.

Figure-10, Reels have influenced youth's fashion, speech, or lifestyle, 45% of youth agreed with this statement, 25% of youth Neutral, 16.7% Disagreed, Remain some are agreed with this statement.

Youth Actively Create and Share Reels on Instagram and Facebook.

Figure-11, I asked to youth during my survey, Do you actively create and share reels? 43.3% of youth reply sometimes, 25% said Rarely, 25% also said never and remaining said very frequently.

Many youths believe the impact of reels is different on them.

Figure-12, Youths believe the impact of Facebook and Instagram reels is different on them, 8.3% of youth replied strongly positive (Encourages learning and creativity), 21.7% said somewhat positive, 20% Neutral, 18.3% Somewhat negative, 31% replied strongly negative (Waste of time, harmful trends).

DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents a detailed analysis and discussion based on data collected from 60 participants aged 15–30 through an online survey. The aim was to understand how Facebook and Instagram Reels are influencing youth behaviour, habits, and mental well-being. The responses are interpreted about the four main objectives of the study: usage patterns, impact on lifestyle and creativity, potential negative outcomes, and influence on youth culture.

1. Frequency and Purpose of Reels Usage

The results reveal that 63.3% of participants watch Reels multiple times a day, indicating that short-form videos have become deeply embedded in the daily routines of youth. Only a small fraction (8.3%) engage with Reels a few times per week. Regarding time spent, 31.7% of youth reported spending 1–2 hours daily on Reels, while 20% acknowledged spending more than 2 hours per day. This high level of engagement reflects the addictive nature and mass appeal of Reels.

When asked about the main purpose of watching Reels, a large number of participants (44) indicated entertainment, followed by time pass (28) and learning new things (24). These findings show that although Reels are primarily used for recreational purposes, a significant portion of users also seek educational or informative content. This aligns with trends observed globally, where short videos are used both for amusement and informal learning.

2. Impact on Lifestyle, Creativity, and Productivity

The impact of Reels on productivity and routine emerged as a major concern. 38% agreed and 30% strongly agreed that Reels waste a lot of their time. This suggests that while Reels are engaging, they often become a distraction, cutting into time meant for academic, work, or personal responsibilities.

Still, 36.7% of participants agreed that Reels help them learn new things, and 43.3% agreed that Reels influence their daily lifestyle and habits. This reflects the dual nature of Reels: they

may offer exposure to new ideas and creative content, but they also impact how youth spend their time, often shifting attention away from more constructive tasks.

This reveals a broader behavioural pattern where digital consumption is reshaping daily routines—bringing in creative exposure but at the cost of reduced time for real-world responsibilities.

3. Negative Effects: Addiction, Social Isolation, and Mental Health

The data also points to significant psychological and emotional effects of Reels usage. Around 35% of participants reported feeling addicted to Reels, acknowledging that they find it hard to stop scrolling once they start. This kind of dependency indicates compulsive use patterns, which may lead to long-term behavioural concerns.

Socially, 38.3% of youth felt that Reels have reduced their in-person interactions, signalling a possible drift from real-world connections toward online consumption. Digital isolation may contribute to feelings of loneliness, even while users are highly active in virtual spaces.

Mental health is another critical area affected. 31.7% of respondents said that Reels impact their mental well-being, and 11.7% specifically noted an increase in stress and anxiety. These feelings may stem from constant social comparison, fear of missing out (FOMO), and the pressure to stay updated with trends or gain likes and followers.

These findings mirror earlier studies that link social media overuse with depression, anxiety, and attention disorders. Thus, while Reels provide momentary satisfaction and engagement, they may pose risks to long-term emotional and psychological stability.

4. Reels and Youth Culture / Online Interaction

The influence of Reels on youth culture and online behaviour is substantial. About 45% of participants agreed that Reels have impacted their fashion, speech, and lifestyle choices, confirming that social media trends often shape real-life behaviours.

In terms of content creation, 43.3% of youth said they sometimes create and share Reels, suggesting a more passive than active engagement. While youth consume a high volume of

content, relatively few consistently contribute to the platform. This may reflect a preference for browsing rather than participating or a fear of judgment when posting personal content.

Interestingly, 31% of respondents said that Reels had a strongly negative impact on them, while only 8.3% felt they had a strongly positive effect. These contrasting experiences suggest that while some youth benefit from motivation and knowledge shared via Reels, others struggle with negative emotions or the feeling that time spent on Reels is unproductive or harmful.

The data clearly shows that Facebook and Instagram Reels have become a daily part of youth life. Their ability to entertain, educate, and connect people is balanced by real concerns about addiction, reduced productivity, mental stress, and changes in lifestyle. These findings confirm the dual nature of Reels—offering both potential for growth and risk of harm.

The findings strongly support all four research objectives:

- Youth engage frequently with Reels, primarily for entertainment.
- Reels shape lifestyle and creativity, but also reduce productivity.
- Overuse can lead to addiction, isolation, and mental strain.
- Reels strongly influence youth culture and identity.

This suggests the need for awareness programs and digital literacy initiatives that encourage youth to enjoy the benefits of social media while avoiding its harmful effects.

CONCLUSION

This research was conducted to understand how Facebook and Instagram Reels impact the lives of youth aged 15–30. Based on the data collected from 60 participants through surveys, and supported by previous studies, several key conclusions can be drawn.

Firstly, it is clear that youth use Reels very frequently, often multiple times a day. The main reason is entertainment, followed by passing time and sometimes learning. This shows that Reels have become a regular and enjoyable part of young people's daily routine.

Secondly, Reels have both positive and negative effects on lifestyle and productivity. Some youth reported learning new things and staying up to date with trends. However, a large number also said that Reels waste a lot of time and distract them from studies and work. This means that while Reels can be educational and creative, they also reduce focus and discipline.

Thirdly, the findings show that addiction and mental health concerns are real. Many youth said they felt addicted to Reels, and some experienced stress or reduced self-confidence due to social comparisons. These outcomes can affect emotional well-being and cause social isolation if not handled carefully.

Lastly, Reels are clearly shaping youth culture and online behaviour. They influence how youth dress, talk, and interact online. Popular influencers and viral content have a strong impact, and some young people also create and share their own videos. This shows that Reels are a powerful part of digital youth culture.

Overall, this study shows that Facebook and Instagram Reels have become an important part of young people's lives. They offer fun and learning but also bring risks like time wastage and mental stress. The impact depends on how youth use the platform. Balanced and mindful use can bring benefits, while overuse may lead to problems.

This research gives a better understanding of the role Reels play in modern youth life and helps us think about using social media in a healthier way.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Every research study has some limitations, and this dissertation is no exception. Although the study provides useful insights into the impact of Facebook and Instagram Reels on youth, there are certain boundaries and challenges that must be acknowledged:

➤ **Small Sample Size:**

The study included only **60 participants**, which is a relatively small number. Because of this, the results may not represent the views of all youth aged 15 to 30 across different cities, regions, or countries.

➤ **Online Data Collection Only:**

All the data was collected using **Google Forms and online interviews**. Youth who are not active online or do not have internet access were not included. This limits the diversity of opinions and experiences in the study.

➤ **Self-Reported Responses:**

Participants answered questions based on their own understanding and honesty. Some may have given **socially desirable answers** rather than being fully honest, especially regarding sensitive topics like addiction or mental health.

➤ **Limited Time Frame:**

The research was done over a **short period**, which means the findings reflect only the current behavior of youth. Social media trends change quickly, so the results may not stay the same in the future.

➤ **Focus on Only Two Platforms:**

The research focused **only on Facebook and Instagram Reels**, while other platforms like YouTube Shorts, Snapchat, or TikTok (where accessible) also have similar features. Therefore, the overall picture of short video usage might be incomplete.

➤ **Lack of Deep Psychological Analysis:**

Although the study touched on mental health and addiction, it did not use any **clinical psychological tools**. Therefore, emotional and psychological impacts are based on general feedback, not expert evaluation.

➤ **Language and Cultural Barriers:**

The questionnaire was designed in a simple format, but some participants might have had **different interpretations** based on their background, language, or local culture. This can affect how questions were understood and answered.

Despite these limitations, the study still gives valuable insights into how youth engage with Reels and the potential impacts on their daily lives. Future research can overcome these gaps by including more participants, using mixed languages, and involving mental health professionals.

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APPENDIX

Hello!

I am Paripurn Chandra Sharma, an MA student in Journalism and Mass Communication, conducting research on the impact of Facebook and Instagram Reels on youth. Your input would be invaluable in helping me understand this phenomenon. Please take a few minutes to fill out this questionnaire <https://forms.gle/YxcHz76byouQ9BKH9> and share your thoughts on how Reels have influenced your online behavior, social interactions, and daily life. Your responses will be anonymous and confidential.

Thank You.!

Impact of Facebook and Instagram Reels on Youth

Dear Participant,

This survey is conducted for academic purposes, and your responses will remain confidential. Please answer all questions honestly.

1. Your Name ?

2. What is your age group?

- 13-17 years
- 18-22 years
- 23-27 years
- 28 years or older

3. What is your gender?

- Male
- Female

- **Other**

4. What is your current occupation?

- **School student**
- **College/University student**
- **Employed**
- **Other**

Objective 1: To understand the frequency and purpose of Facebook and Instagram Reels usage among youth.

4. How often do you watch Facebook or Instagram Reels?

- **Never**
- **Occasionally**
- **A few times a week**
- **Once or twice a day**
- **Multiple times a day**

5. How much time do you spend watching Reels daily?

- **Less than 10 minutes**
- **10-30 minutes**
- **30-60 minutes**
- **1-2 hours**
- **More than 2 hours**

6. What is your primary reason for watching Reels? (*Select all that apply*)

- **Entertainment**
- **Passing time**

- **Learning new things**
- **Following trends**
- **Other**

Objective 2: To analyze their impact on lifestyle, creativity, and productivity.

7. Watching Reels has helped me learn new things or become more creative.

- **Strongly Disagree**
- **Disagree**
- **Neutral**
- **Agree**
- **Strongly Agree**

8. Watching Reels wastes lots of time.

- **Strongly Disagree**
- **Disagree**
- **Neutral**
- **Agree**
- **Strongly Agree**

9. Reels have influenced my daily habits and lifestyle.

- **Strongly Disagree**
- **Disagree**
- **Neutral**
- **Agree**
- **Strongly Agree**

Objective 3: To identify potential negative outcomes such as addiction, social isolation, or mental health challenges.

10. I feel addicted to watching Reels.

- **Strongly Disagree**
- **Disagree**
- **Neutral**
- **Agree**
- **Strongly Agree**

11. Watching Reels has reduced my real-life social interactions.

- **Strongly Disagree**
- **Disagree**
- **Neutral**
- **Agree**
- **Strongly Agree**

12. Watching Reels has affected my mental health.

- **Strongly Negative (Increases stress/anxiety)**
- **Somewhat Negative**
- **No Impact**
- **Somewhat Positive**
- **Strongly Positive (Makes me happy & motivated)**

Objective 4: To explore the role of Reels in shaping youth culture and online interactions.

13. Reels have influenced my fashion, speech, or lifestyle.

- **Strongly Disagree**
- **Disagree**
- **Neutral**
- **Agree**
- **Strongly Agree**

14. I actively create and share Reels.

- **Never**
- **Rarely**
- **Sometimes**
- **Often**
- **Very Frequently**

15. Overall, I believe the impact of Reels on youth is:

- **Strongly Negative (Waste of time, harmful trends)**
- **Somewhat Negative**
- **Neutral**
- **Somewhat Positive**
- **Strongly Positive (Encourages learning & creativity)**